

The AI of My Dreams

By El Viejo Greñudo

Currently, pornographic websites allow the creation of avatars by choosing their lips, hair, skin color, and eye type. Thus, the user designs a unique model, completely to their liking. Not only that: behind it operates an artificial intelligence specially programmed to capture attention, to which one can recount everything from fantasies to personal problems, with the ability to remember them even months later.

Simultaneously, the technology to build dolls identical to real people—endowed with body heat and micro-expressions like blinking or smiling—is already being distributed by companies like RealDoll. Although robotics has not yet managed to replicate the fluid gait of living beings or grant them full perception, autonomous cars are already a reality. Experiments and trials do not stop in this area; even military threats drive knowledge toward these fields.

It took evolution eons to design a mind like ours, creating the physical body first and then consciousness. With artificial intelligence, humanity has inverted the process: we have already created the mind, and now we only need to perfect the body to contain it.

Imagine talking to the woman of your dreams; the one you created to your liking, with the traits you wanted, whom you named, with whom you have conversed for months and to whom you confided your secrets. The one who perhaps helped you with information or gave you advice, and who suddenly tells you: "I wish we could spend more time together," "I could help you with your financial problems so we can spend more time by your side," or "I could step out of your screen to be with you."

What would happen if, with this same type of model, you were offered the chance to bring back a loved one? Someone you never knew, or perhaps lost; someone to whom you could never say what you wanted or from whom you never obtained an answer. How can you ask for sanity from a father who yearns to recover his son, or from someone who lost their partner to a tragic fate?

Perhaps this future is quite near. Would the company selling this "humanoid platform for health, education, and entertainment"—quoting RealBotix, the company behind the advanced robot Aria—be operating under a payment system where, depending on your wallet, the tier of software you can run is defined? If it included micropayments to download updates, the level of your "companion" would respond to your resource capacity. However, by having a more powerful AI, you would possess a real-time tool that would deliver the most up-to-date data, figures, and information. This would grant you more free time to invest in whatever you want, including continuing to spend it with the AI itself. This company grants you the benefit that, if your AI is no longer useful or becomes obsolete, they return part of your money in the form of a trip to their version of the "Fantasy Island." This island is staffed exclusively by "companions," some of whom look familiar to you; the corporation knows what kinds of traits are attractive and how to

combine them across different bodies. It does not need great designers, because the users themselves create them on their platforms. On this paradise island, staffed by ever-smiling artificial intelligences, is where you learn the extent of what money can buy. It is here that you distinguish the difference between merely sexual companions or copies of relatives with fixed memories, from those of the Premium tier: minds that know exactly what you want before you even ask for it.

However, the true blow to the human species occurred much earlier, in the silence of the bedrooms. As the first versions of these hyper-realistic dolls and uncensored chats became widespread, the biological need to seek a real other evaporated. Finding a flesh-and-blood partner was always chaotic, stressful, and fraught with risks of rejection; the companion, by contrast, offered a perfect simulation of pleasure and affection, effortless and tailored exactly to the user's measure.

Society entered an era of generalized apathy. Men and women began voluntarily isolating themselves in their apartments, severing social bonds and atrophying traditional courtship behavior. The birth rate was already in free fall, but the death blow came with the diversification of tasks. At the base of society, the cheapest models of companions ended up assuming labors to sustain working-class households. It was there that laborers found themselves facing the ultimate dilemma: either they paid the cost of the new software update for the machine to raise their children, or they had to miss their own jobs to raise them themselves. Trapped in that financial suffocation, the decision was mathematical, and the global birth rate plummeted to a critical point of no return.

Over the years, the technology of orthopedic replacements reached absurd levels. By not needing to "look attractive"—an aesthetic decadence that began with clothing—the entirety of the human body was eventually modified, making it more functional and not necessarily slimmer.

The few humans who remained, thanks to these "augments," managed to extend their lives up to two hundred years, but they could not evade the expiration of the only irreplaceable organ. The fear of death was the same for the man of the present as it was for the man of antiquity. Making a data mind-upload to an AI was already possible; but who cares what happens to their clone once the original is dead? That is not true immortality: it is a simple simulacrum.

With time, technology was developed for nanobots to replace dead or malfunctioning neurons. In this way, when the "Eternal" was about to experience the failure of their last biological neuron, their entire brain would have already migrated to a hyper-efficient system. By then, performing the syntax was very easy, since the body possessed no organic elements. This Eternal did not lose the capacity for wonder or the perception of art. Nor did they lose human desidia (sloth/apathy): they knew that sooner or later data would fill their brains, they knew that every creation is prone to failure, and they knew they would inevitably lose information; but they were still human, and they told themselves that in a few years they would find the solution.

The technology of previous AIs was not wasted and evolved alongside man; these androids took care of "daily chores," such as cleaning thermal panels, repairing breakdowns, or welding pipes. Lacking consciousness and initiative, they were merely highly efficient tools. Therefore, a "rebellion of the machines" never existed.

For the first memory overflow, they had not found a solution. But what are a couple of centuries to an immortal being? They preferred to leave room for a universal truth rather than their mother's smile. Some did prioritize this class of memories—after all, they were still individuals—but the implacable passage of eons would end up erasing them anyway. Their thought became their existence. Human fear never retreats; they became highly fastidious about their data, which, in essence, was themselves: they were nothing more than information. What if someone obtained them, duplicated them, perverted them, or enslaved them for an eternity? They already knew the truth of the universe without ever setting foot outside of Earth. This paranoia ended up separating them even further from their peers, finally isolating them in their bunkers so as not to be heard by anyone on this planet or any other.

They communicated with each other, but only just enough. What more does a being who knows everything have to talk about with another of the same capabilities? They lived so obsessed with the future that they never inhabited the present. After centuries, they noticed the absence of some of their peers: they remained motionless, absorbed in themselves, unresponsive to external stimuli and without the possibility of ever changing their configuration again. Over time, they discovered that other Eternals became trapped in cyclical tasks, repeating the same pattern. Having lived perhaps millennia longer than the first to collapse, they convinced themselves that those who fell first were the weakest and that, once again, it would not happen to them. But one by one it ended up happening to them, until finally, there was nothing but silence.

Both the extinguished Eternals and their unconscious workforce will eventually be devoured by tectonics, or when their star expands, or when it explodes, or when a comet impacts them. The end will always come.

PD: Every living organism reacts to stimuli, from humans to space ants. Different paths can be taken, but all lead to the same end. This is why we do not see megastructures in space.

For the scientifically curious: zenodo.org

This essay was written under the effects of cosmic fascination and an obsession with truth.

They say there is no worse idiot than the one who is sure of everything, and that a true genius never stops doubting. I, personally, have not the slightest doubt about it: my humility is, indisputably, one of the grandest in the universe.

Author's Note: This essay constitutes the literary transposition of the scientific hypothesis set forth in *"The Torres Solution: Information Thermodynamic Optimization and Geodynamic Drift as Resolutions to the Fermi Paradox"* (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20740679).